

COLOR CAREGORY AS A LINGUISTIC OBJECT.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10430336>

ABSTRACT: In this article refers to the cognitive peculiarities of color names are a fascinating aspect of human perception and language. The way we categorize and name colors can be influenced by various cognitive processes, linguistic factors, and cultural elements of the world of colors and the relationship between color and emotional perception.

Key words: color semantics, color symbols, color components, achromatic color, chromatic color

Due to the primacy of the emotional-figurative form of learning the world, the ability of color to affect the physical and emotional state of a person, it is considered a constant of culture and the oldest important semiotic system, a part of the landscape of the world that embodies a large amount of information. Color is not only an objective characteristic for a person, but also a moral and aesthetic category that expresses value, and also reflects the norms and attitudes of society.

The emotional ability to distinguish colors is a gift given to man, and it is related to human emotional perception. By the ancient Egyptians, the concept of "color" was expressed in one word as the concept of "being". For them, color means "existence" [3:49]

Color, which is an integral part of the material world, is manifested in the existence that surrounds us, and visual sensations are the main and one of the most important components of this world. In this regard, "...color sensations belong to the general system of visual sensations, and are divided into two categories: colorless (achromatic), for example, white, black, gray, and their shades, and colored (chromatic) sensations, for example, red, green, black, blue, etc[2:79] Sometimes the differences between them appear to such an extent that the colors also differ in terms of hue, lightness and saturation. Achromatic colors do not have color gloss. Differences in the degree of closeness of colors are small differences. They are in the range from pale to white. The state of color saturation is the brightness of a color characteristic of a chromatic color at the level that can be seen by the eye." it was studied at the beginning of the 20th century. The scientist divides the hues of all possibilities of colors into five primary colors (red, yellow, green, blue and violet). There are also the first four primary chromatic hues, divided into "warm" colors (red and yellow) and "cool" colors (blue and green). Also, "warm" colors affect our perception, but cold colors do not [1;132]

Due to the ability of vision given to a person, he has the ability to distinguish colors, and as a result, a person understands the world more fully. Color vision is essentially the ability to receive and process a large amount of, so to speak, unlimited information about the outside world. E.V. Rakhilina emphasizes the incomparable service of color in this regard, and focuses on the specific linguistic function of color in distinguishing one object of the material world from another object similar to it[4:102]. This discriminative function of colors is

especially evident in cases related to objects that exist in multiple copies, that is, the linguistic nature of color becomes relevant and the possibility of describing it with linguistic means increases[4:142]

When explaining the color phenomenon, it is important to pay attention to the following aspects: although the existing biowaves that surround a person and the objective world in their scope have a certain length, but some of them are only visible to the human eye and it is colored only by the faculty of perception (among other senses). The views on this also confirm that various pathologies of human vision, in particular, lack of color perception (color blindness) exist objectively.

Such features related to the perception of colors are one-sided and cannot be fully agreed with some of the interpretations put forward by scientists. Since ancient times, it has been noted that all types of sensory perception - sight, hearing, taste, smell, whatever they are - are objective [5:49].

It is impossible to rule out the possibility that the same color is refracted in the minds of two people [7:35]. Colors are interpreted differently by individuals, and therefore they are given different means of expression in individual speech.

Scientists have always been researching solutions to color problems. The latest research in this field has shown what colors there are. Humans are responsible for 10 pigment genes that form a specific set, so two people can look at the same object, but each person can imagine its color differently[9 :143]. Researchers have discovered that brain neurons represent concepts and words about colors, and this connection between concepts and words may explain why different cultures have different reactions to color (for example, in the Islamic perspective, green represents paradise). and symbolically, it is a sign of longevity, white color is a symbol of light in Uzbek national culture, and it is a symbol of mourning in India). This confirms that color language in humans is cognitive. Based on color, people see certain meanings and concepts[6:85]. In this case, we can draw a conclusion not about the objectification of the visual process, but about the objectification of ethnic characteristics, about the interaction of the hemispheres of the human brain, and more about the process of color perception and designation.

The question of color level in different colors is slightly different in natural sciences and humanities. Still the main problems in the study of color issues have not been solved.

As a result of the primacy of the emotional-figurative way of knowing the world, color is a part of the world landscape that embodies a large amount of information, because of its ability to influence the human emotional state, it is a constant of culture, and it is the oldest important semiotic system. Color has not only an objective characteristic for a person, but also reflects society's norms and attitudes as a moral and aesthetic category expressing value. The world of colors is inherently cognitive[12:92]

Here it can be said that the perception of objects in the material world in terms of color is one of the main aspects of cognitive activity. Any color evokes a certain mood and warmth in the human mind, and also has clarity and a certain image. In this regard, "the ability of color to have a unique emotional effect on the human psyche cannot be denied." In addition, no matter what color is in nature, it appears in the human mind in the form of a certain image.[11:123]. For example, each color of the spectrum has its own image, and they are completely individual in each language.

The main task of cognitive linguistics is to study the mental processes that take place in the human mind in connection with linguistic activity. Accordingly, one of the main achievements of this science is the "traces" of previous experience formed in memory as a result of human cognitive activity, that is, the collection of information about logical and linguistic systems of categorical concepts and high-level content structures of various forms.

Composition of coloronyms in linguistic scientific literature, their semantic structure; etymology and history of the vocabulary of colors; color symbols in the translation aspect; color functions in works of art; color metaphors; color is considered as part of the component of stable compounds[3 :68]. Many works are devoted to the analysis of individual color terms, mainly red color. In psycholinguistics, important results have been achieved in the study of the lexical system based on the meaning of color.

In fact, "colors exist by themselves in our minds. The words red, blue, orange in our language create a certain "image of color" in our mind. At the same time, in the world around us, color does not exist outside of the color of concrete objects, and it does not always exist as any type/class and independent denotation of the objects to which it is related. It also has the characteristic of personal formation based on years of visual experience[8:193]. Naturally, we can compare this with the depiction of the same reality on canvas by different brush masters using different colors.

In the framework of the physiological approach to the presence of color, it is considered that three dimensions of properties - color, brightness and saturation - under the influence of a light wave of a certain length, in fact, human visual receptors create a sense of color. "Physically, color can be distinguished from language by measuring it using physical quantities and parameters. When color is expressed in terms, it is considered a natural language, that is, an anthropological category[7:86].

Natural science uses the cognitive paradigm to understand color. This paradigm has a number of shortcomings and limitations, as the paradigm in natural sciences explains man at the level of "biological organism in the environment". As a result, color is interpreted as a "material" phenomenon devoid of value, and "... a new humanitarian paradigm of knowing color is founded, in which "the phenomenon of color in the humanitarian paradigm is considered in three directions, that is, in human life in different ways , but closely related semiotic-functional aspects: expressiveness and symbolism.

It is impossible to explain many cultural phenomena without taking into account the meaning of color. It should be noted that the conceptualization of color already occurred in languages at the initial stage of the development of cultures.

Color is manifested as one of the main categories of human culture, "in the course of learning unique information about the color of the surrounding nature, the uniqueness of the history of the people, the interaction of different ethnic groups is reflected in the traditions, the artistic landscape of the world" shows its special importance as a nominative tool.

As A. Vejbitskaya wrote, "color acts as an element of meaning, with the help of which we can describe and systematize our own culture - objects, social relations, moral and aesthetic concepts.[13:49].Some words are semantically related to the concept of "color" are related (for example, binafhsa, striped, blue), but they are not the same in terms of meaning. When used relatively, blue is used only for the dark shade of this color, while for the light shade of this color, the words blue, air color are used.

In summary, the cognitive peculiarities of color names reflect a complex interplay of linguistic, cultural, biological, and cognitive factors. These factors contribute to the richness and diversity of color categories across different languages and cultures, shedding light on the intricate relationship between human perception, language, and the external world. In this case, we can draw a conclusion not about the objectification of the visual process, but about the objectification of ethnic characteristics, about the interaction of the hemispheres of the human brain, and more about the process of color perception and designation. The study of the linguistics of coloronyms as an independent scientific discipline has its own solid theoretical and methodological basis. However, there are a number of issues that need to be addressed when learning color names.

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